

TEACHER EDUCATION IN VARANASI CITY: A SURVEY REPORT

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This excerpt from Earth Summit+5:

Programme for the further Implementation of Agenda 21 describes the role of education in fostering more sustainable societies.

*“Education increases human welfare, and is a decisive factor in enabling people to become productive and responsible members of society. A fundamental prerequisite for sustainable development is an adequately financed and effective educational system at all levels, particularly the primary and secondary levels, that is accessible to all and that augments both human capacity and well being. The core themes of education for sustainability include lifelong learning, interdisciplinary education, partnerships, multicultural education and empowerment. Priority should be given to ensuring women’s and girls’ full and equal access to all levels of education and training. Special attention should also be paid to the **training of teachers**, youth leaders and other educators. Education should also be seen as a means of empowering youth and vulnerable and marginalized groups, including those in rural areas, through intergenerational partnerships and peer education. Even in countries with strong education systems, there is a need to reorient education, awareness and training so as to promote*

widespread public understanding, critical analysis and support for sustainable development. (p 74)''

The success of an educational system depends most of all on the quality of the teacher. With the advent of standard-based reforms, the quality of teachers has become a major concern of policy-makers, college and university presidents, especially at the colleges of teacher education, and the public in general. Every child deserves a quality teacher. In an era of increasing standards and accountability in education, teacher quality and teacher training will be more important than ever.

Education everywhere is now in Ukase. Teacher Education today has an uphill task to negotiate numerous inconsistencies related to education for qualitative change. The challenges of Teacher Education cannot but encompass different parameters of education- aesthetic and creative education, national cohesion, development of basic skills, socio-aesthetic excellence and innovative approaches to evaluation. The role of teacher educators in teacher education has assumed special significance, since teachers today are entrusted with the serene task of enkindling the spirit of global awareness among pupils.

Realizing that the quality of the teachers as long regarded is a professional responsibility rather than a policy issue, and the need to evolve a framework and evaluation tool to help institutions in quality assurance and continuous improvement, the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC), India in collaboration with the Commonwealth of Learning (COL), Canada, has initiated the process of developing Quality Indicators for Teacher Education. The initiative has brought together teacher educators, quality assurance experts and policy

makers from around eleven Common wealth countries. Experts from Australia, Bangladesh, Botswana, India, Kenya, Mauritius, Namibia, Nigeria, Sri Lanka, Singapore and United Kingdom (U.K.), participated in the initial workshop and subsequent development process. The Expert Group was tasked with identifying and short listing the potential indicators for quality teacher education and arriving at a framework encompassing all aspects of a TEI's functioning comprehensively.

The experts met and deliberated in a series of workshops held in India over a year and through online discussions held during this period. They had identified 75 quality indicators which were classified under six Key areas. These key areas are

- **Curriculum Design and Planning**
- **Curriculum Transaction and Evaluation**
- **Research, Development and Extension**
- **Infrastructure and Learning Resources**
- **Student Support and Progression**
- **Organisation and Management**

If the quality factors are not maintained properly we cannot think of excellence in teacher education programme. Keeping this in mind the researcher took up the present topic entitled "Status of teacher education in Varanasi city".

Objectives of the present study:

The main objective of the present study is to assess the key areas of the teacher education institutions of Varanasi city.

Sample:

Varanasi was the sheet of learning since Puranic age. At present five universities are there in Varansi city i.e

- Banaras Hindu University,
- Mahatma Gandhi Kasi Vidyapith, Sampurnanand Sanskrit University,
- Vir bahadur Purvanchal University and
- Central university of Tibetan Studies.

As it is well known for learning and great scholars, the researcher decided to take up Varanasi as the place and all the teacher education institutions as the sample for study. The institutions are of two types i.e. Govt. and private. There are nine govt. B.Ed. colleges whereas nine private B.Ed. colleges.

Govt. B.Ed. College:

- Faculty of education, Kamaccha, Varanasi
- Vasanta college for Women, Rajghat, Varanasi
- Arya Mahila P.G. College, Varanasi
- R.G.S.C., Barkachha
- Mahatma Gandhi Kasi Vidyapith, Varanasi
- Harishchandra P.G. College, Varanasi
- Udaypratap college, Varanasi
- Sampurnanand Sanskrit University, Varanasi

- Central institute of Tibetan studies, Sarnath, Varanasi.

Private B.Ed. Colleges:

- Institute of Education, SHEPA Campus, Varanasi
- Sudhakar Mahila P.G. College, Varanasi
- Dharendra Mahila college, Varanasi
- Mahadev Mahavidyalaya, Varanasi
- Jeevandeep college, Varanasi
- Abhaya Mahavidyala, Varanasi
- Jayaprakash Mahavidyalaya, Varanasi
- Ghanshyam B.Ed. College, Varanasi
- M.P. Institute ,Varanasi

Procedure of the study:

The researcher personally visited to each colleges and collected the data in five point scale as per the format given by NAAC.

Analysis and Interpretation of the data:

CURRICULUM DESIGN AND PLANNING

Quality aspects	Performance level Govt. Colleges	Performance level Private Colleges
Institutional Vision	2	1
Process of	2	2

curriculum design		
Curriculum Content	2	2

CURRICULUM TRANSACTION AND EVALUATION

Quality aspects	Performance level Govt. Colleges	Performance level Private Colleges
Curriculum Revision	2	2
Induction/Orientation	3	1
Transaction of Theory	1	1
Transaction of Practical Experiences	1	1
Assessment and Evaluation	2	1
Teacher and Teaching	2	1

RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT AND EXTENSION

Quality aspects	Performance level Govt. Colleges	Performance level Private Colleges
Research and Development	3	1
Community Engagement	2	1

INFRASTRUCTURE AND LEARNING RESOURCES

Quality aspects	Performance level Govt. Colleges	Performance level Private Colleges
Physical Infrastructure	2	1
Instructional Infrastructure	1	1
Human Resources	3	1

STUDENT SUPPORT AND PROGRESSION

Quality aspects	Performance level Govt. Colleges	Performance level Private Colleges
System Efficiency	2	1
Feedback Mechanism	2	1
Diagnosis and Remedial Programme	1	1
Guidance and Counseling Service	1	1
Admission Procedure	3	3

ORGANISATION MANAGEMENT

Quality aspects	Performance level Govt. Colleges	Performance level Private Colleges
Social, Cultural and Leisure Activities	3	1
Internal Coordination and Management	3	2
Academic Calendar	3	2

Faculty Recruitment	4	2
Financial Governance	4	2
Academic Quality and Management	3	1

From these data it is clear that the performance level of Govt. colleges are better than the Private colleges but both the institution do not have proper quality index as per the format.

Suggestions:

To improve the quality of the teacher education programme mostly all the key areas should be developed.

- Most of the teacher training institutions do not have clear mission which is the dire necessity for an institution to run. So, they should have a well specified mission and vision to work.
- Curriculum is not designed as per NCFTE-2009. So, the old stereotyped curriculum still exists. In this respect the teacher education curriculum of Varanasi city (Banaras Hindu University, mahatma Gandhi Kasi Vidyapitha, Sampurnand Sanskrit University, and Central institute of Tibetan studies) is lagging behind. So, the curriculum should be modified and proper content should be included in the curriculum.

